

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ARTISTIC-AESTHETIC SHADES OF GHAZAL IN AZERBAIJANI POETRY OF THE EARLY 20th CENTURY

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Abstract

The beginning of the 20th century can be considered the beginning of a new and more complicated stage of socio-economic development, literary-cultural, national-ideological thought, social-political thinking, enlightenment movement in the socio-political and cultural life of Azerbaijan. During this period, Azerbaijani literature was developing against the background of multifaceted and rich literary processes. Azerbaijani literature, especially poetry, created in the synthesis of Eastern and Western social and cultural thought, literary and artistic trends, was noticeable as a synthesis of tradition and innovation in terms of its unique idea, theme, form and genre. Poetry reflecting the issues of concerning to society, the inner world, mental state, thoughts and ideals of a person has been created in a colorful and unique form. In addition to the national ideology, the Azerbaijani literary and artistic thought of the beginning of the 20th century, when Western tendencies has been widespread, has reflected both the progressive aspects of European literature and new literary trends, as well as the development of classical literary traditions in terms of ideas and craftsmanship. In this sense, Azer Buzovnali, Aliabbas Muznib and Samad Mansur, who are prominent representatives of Azerbaijani lyrics of the beginning of the 20th century, whose creativity being rich in romantic-amorous, social, patriotic, religious-didactic, philosophical-sufian, national-ideological, humanist motives, attracts attention. In the poems written by them in ghazal genre, the different poles of life, the dreams and aspirations of society, the ideals of freedom and progress are glorified in a highly artistic language. The lyrics of all three poets, which are colorful in terms of content and ideas and include new trends, preserve their traditionality in terms of form and genre.

Keywords: Azerbaijani, classical poetry, literary tradition, Azer, Muznib, Samad Mansur, ghazal.

INTRODUCTION

In the first half of the 20th century, the world became a field of spiritual and cultural innovations formed in the turmoil and grip of revolutions and changes. Western tendencies, formed in the context of Eurocentrism, anthropocentrism and altruism ideas, culturally and politically included the literary sphere in its stream as well. Although the development of reforms and bourgeois-capitalist relations brought out Western tendencies, the national ideological current in the national centers, as well as in Azerbaijan, was diversifying as a part of the ideology of enlightenment. In the 19th century, the ideas of national-enlightenment formed and developed by prominent Azerbaijani intellectuals such as M.F. Akhundzade, H. Zardabi, through progressive magazines such as "Akinchi" and later "Molla Nasreddin" began to be spread more widely by thoughtful intellectuals, writers and poets in the first half of the 20th century, especially in the 20s and 30s. Now the spirit of freedom, cultural and social ideals of the West have been synthesized with the emotional, romantic spirit, national and spiritual ideals of the East, new shades and innovative views were forming in the East-West cultural unity in order to save the homeland and the nation from both material and spiritual slavery, as well as from cultural and social inertia. On the one hand, the society looked at the West as a center of social and political freedom, and on the other hand, as a place that stimulated the development of science and culture against the background of anthropocentrism. In this sense, the 20th century constitutes a great stage in the

history of the world and Azerbaijan against the background of the complexity of political and economic events and the multifacetedness of the cultural and social situation. The first half of the 20th century, which is a part of a hundred-year period, is a historical period with unique cultural and social shades, sharp changes, inertia and revolutions, renaissance and decline. The literary-artistic thought of the era, which was dominated by the innovative and national spirit and was created in the unity of progressive ideals, is a reflection of the social-political, cultural-spiritual life in the country, a figurative reflection of what is happening in the life of the society, an art painting described by words. In particular, let us note that the national social opinion, Eastern romanticism and Western realism pass to a leading position in fiction with romantic-secular motifs.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Azerbaijan literature of the 20th century reflects contradictory and complex processes, multifaceted cultural revolutions, spiritual and social explosions, and also attracts attention from the point of view of reflection of national issues, national identity and national values. The literature of this period emerges either as a literary trend that reflects new tendencies, developed against the background of social and cultural development of the West, or as a literature that preserves classical traditions, historical-literary trends.

National-spiritual values, national identity thought were revived against the background of human values and the unity of East-West scientific-philosophical

thought in poetry, which became more popular due to the wider spread and mass of literature. Azerbaijan's prominent writers thought that as a result of adopting the Western way of thinking and living, science and cultural advancement, the society would get rid of the outdated scholastic moral principles veiled by religion, socio-political dependence, and they would be able to build a happy and democratic life and a new society. Of course, the intellectuals who grew up in the literary and cultural environment of Istanbul had a big role in the strengthening of Western tendencies. It should also be noted that at the beginning of the 20th century, the Western views that appeared in Azerbaijan's literary-artistic and social opinion were based on national unity and love for national spiritual and moral values. In this sense, the idea that *"intellectuals while becoming familiar with the West, became more attached to the national-spiritual roots - Turkism and Islam, and highly appreciated their human essence, far from any kind of chauvinism"* is completely right [2, p. 6]. Mir Jalal, an eminent literary critic, who analyzed the literary-artistic thought that arose against the background of complex historical conditions, writes as follows: *"In the history of Azerbaijan, fictional literature has never been closely connected with the necessary social issues of the day until now, it has never covered these issues to the extent it does today. Literature has never been read so much, and it has never evoked such a quick and wide response in society"* [14, p. 70].

The merits of poetry as well as the press are great in promoting enlightenment, assimilation of the Western cultural level, as well as popularization of national values and moral principles that will lead the society to progress. In this sense, in the first half of the 20th century, it is undeniable that poetry, which is the yeast of Azerbaijani literature, has the power to awaken the people, assimilate cultural values, and promote integration into the world civilization. However, there were different poles in poetry in expressing these values, ideals, in different ways and means, and in which literary form was used. *"In this period, we see the existence of two poles in the works of most representatives of Azerbaijani poetry. In most of such poetic examples, on the one hand, the traditional genres of the classical style were being preserved, and on the other hand, were being turned to the new content and form reflecting the changes occurring in society and the world. In the literary and artistic environment dominated by conflicting socio-political worldviews, new faces and trends of Azerbaijani literature were forming"* [6, p. 17].

As mentioned, examples of art were creating in all genres and forms of fictional creativity in Azerbaijani literature. *"Our writers and poets, who glorified various issues of public life, dreams and aspirations of the people, ideals of freedom and progress with high artistic language, included both classical literary traditions and folk creativity, as well as modern artistic tendencies in their works. Poetry was the most popular genre of our literature, which developed at the junction of two complicated centuries"* [6, p.18]. National and realistic-humanist motifs formed in Azerbaijani poetry in the all-Turkish literary context and against the background of

classical Eastern literary traditions, determined the directions of literary thought for a long period of time. Almost, in Azerbaijani poetry, which appeared in the first half of the 20th century, or rather, a kind of cultural-spiritual and logical continuation of the centuries before it, along with examples of folk poetry, classical poetry genres still maintained their relevance and mass, and ghazal occupied the most special position at this level. A part of the literary world gave place to journalistic style, allegorical, satirical short stories and quatrains, while the other part turned to a more traditional method, they turned to ghazal genre to embody the new ideological principles of the new era with classical poetry traditions. It must be admitted that the addition of new ideas, artistic shades and innovative traditions to the artistic capacity of ghazal genre, which at first glance seems to many to be a simple and easy genre, undoubtedly it originates from the skill of a word master, the revelation of the aesthetic feeling based on his deep observations, and the method and content of the artistic attitude to the word. However, since ghazal, like all genres of classical poetry, has an ancient history and rich artistic traditions, it is very difficult to add modernity to the artistic capacity of each example created in this genre, and it depends on the individual style and artistic "I" of each word master. The realist and romantic shades available in classical poetic examples were reflected in the background of the development of literary and artistic thought of the period, in the base of national and human tendencies of the literary process. In Azerbaijani poetry of the beginning of the 20th century, we observe the polarization of two directions in terms of ideology, topic and idea, as well as in terms of form, genre and style. On the one hand, the rich examples of folk poetry, which kept alive the general Turkish poetry traditions, and on the other hand, the classical poetry genres, which were faithful to the established rules of Eastern poetry, played the role of a mirror of the society. The idea of Academician Nizami Jafarov, who touched on the features of massification and popularity of poetry genres in Azerbaijani literature, *"in the history of Azerbaijani poetry, two genres have not only distinguished by their special popularity, but also the names of these genres have become symbols of two stylistic directions of national poetry, one is ghazal, the other is goshma"* [12] emerged as a scientific-theoretical result of the reality of this tendency.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The national ideological thought, humanism and patriotism, justice and freedom, national identity and national roots that characterize the beginning of the 20th century Azerbaijani literature as a whole, almost, have become a leitmotif of the creativity of Azer Buzovnali, Alabbas Muznib and Samad Mansur, who created the most beautiful examples of ghazal genre in the 20th century. In the poems written by them in ghazal genre, enlightened-innovative, national ideological tendencies have been presented in the light of moral values such as justice, friendship, honesty, love, responsibility, and patriotism. National identity and national ideological worldview, idea-aesthetic education, enlightened thinking attract attention as the main motives of the poetic heritage of these writers. From this point of view, in the

poetic works of Azer Buzovnali, Aliabbas Muznib, Samad Mansur, Mujtahidzade, as well as in the works of other contemporary poets, on the one hand, we see the continuation of classical literary traditions, on the other hand, we see that these traditions are accompanied by innovation on a new level, against the background of the tendencies of the new era.

In the works of Azer Buzovnali, Mujtahidzade, A. Muznib, most of whose works date back the first half of the 20th century, the influence of the thematic content of old Turkish poetry is felt, and the dominance of the codified literary laws of Eastern poetics is observed. These writers, whose poems with lyrical content and socio-political spirit being published in magazines "Irshad", "Teze Hayat", "Ittifag", "Sada", "Sadayih-aqq", "Basirat", "Zanbur", "Dirilik", "Babayi-Amir", "Molla Nasreddin", "Ingilab alovları", "Sharg gadini" under various nicknames, pseudonyms or official names these word masters were familiar with all the intricacies of classical poetry, they created beautiful examples in ghazal genre, in addition to gasida, takhmis, tarjibband. The creativity of these word masters, who were considered the successors of the classical tradition in Azerbaijani poetry at the beginning of the 20th century, conveyed a new content. The prominent literary scholar, M. Guluzade, paid attention to this issue and rightly wrote that "the critical attitude of Fuzuli's poetry to social injustice, shariat doctrines, and the use of his mastership, artistic form and stylistic feature" [10, p.403] became the main tool of the beginning of the 20th century Azerbaijani poetry.

The word masters who knew the lyrical-emotional burden of ghazal genre and the ability to reflect emotions with colorful shades used ghazal to express their attitude to all the concepts and events surrounding the society and human nature, aimed their words with ghazal, and waged their struggles with ghazal. In these poems, not only the glorification of lyrical passion, love, humanism, and beauty, but also the fight against scholastic outlook, conservatism, and ignorance also played a major role. We can observe the first examples of Turkish-language poetic thought in ghazals, which keep alive the genre and features of Arabic-Persian poetry, created in the various bahrs of aruz, even in the Middle Ages. This tendency, of course, was more dynamic and more clearly noticeable in the works of Aliabbas Muznib, Azer Buzovnali and Samad Mansur who were not indifferent to the social and cultural events of the period in which they lived and created at the beginning of the 20th century, and fought against tyranny, injustice, slavery and invasion, ignorance and backwardness with both their social activities and pens. In their ghazals, which reflect the technical features of Eastern poetics, they revealed the rhyming possibilities of Azerbaijani poetry and the beauty of expression by alternating long and short vowels by using bahrs of aruz in accordance with the rules of our mother tongue. In this sense, we read in ghazal written by A. Buzovnali, also known as Mashadi Azer, and distinguished by its simple language and fluidity:

*Qəlbi-zarimdə nə vardır qüssədən, qəmdən səva,
Ya bu aqlar gözlərimdə nə olar dəmdən səva* [4].

All three poets' ghazals of were beautiful examples of artistic-aesthetic thought, but they were also performers of sincere love, pure love, propagandists of humanism and compassion. Academician N. Jafarov, who considers ghazal "an innovation of the medieval Muslim culture", while talking about ghazal heritage of Samad Mansur, calls him the greatest follower of the Fuzuli literary school in the 20th century, writes that Samad Mansur's talent and style meet the traditional functional requirements of classical ghazal poetry and do not exceed traditional poetic standards [12]. Poet, who wrote in many genres of classical poetry, created beautiful examples in ghazal genre with unique artistic shades:

*Bitə hicran odu, əğyarə vüsəl olsa da qismət,
Min təşəkkür ki, bu müştəqin olub cövrünə layiq* [13, p. 19].

In their ghazals of amorous-love, the poets glorify pure love, expression of admiration of lover, lover's complaints, longing and desire, and the hypocrisy of the foe form the main line of the lyrics like a red line. In this sense, in the lyrical ghazals of Azer Buzovnali, love attracts attention as a factor that elevates, perfects, and spiritually cleanses a person:

*Guşeyi-ləlində xalın hər görün əylər güman,
Məskən etmiş əlbət Hindü kənar zəməmi* [8, p.160].

Through ghazal, which is the translation of lyrical emotions, A. Muznib also emphasizes the greatness, magnificence of love, that it conquers everything, conveys in figurative language that the feelings of friendship, loyalty, truthfulness, and sincerity are at the foundation of love, which is the expression of a person's inner world and spiritual world. A. Muznib, a famous publicist, literary critic, publisher, linguist of his time, was also a ghazal poet with a delicate feeling:

*Dilbəra, mehri-dilin hicrana salmışdır məni,
İntizarın naləvü əfğanə salmışdır məni* [15, p.69].

The ability to describe the lyrical-aesthetic value of ghazal as a glorification of beauties, love, and the feelings of a lover and beloved towards each other was typical of S. Mansur's pen with a revolutionary spirit:

*Vəsli-canan ləzzətin pərvanə yana-yana nəql
Eylər idi müstəməndani-fəraqi-yara duş...* [13, p.25]

Along with the highest human emotions, sublime feelings, and mystical thoughts, the social contradictions of the time were also reflected in ghazals of all three poets with a different style and unique expression. In Samad Mansur's poem expressing his sympathy for the national government overthrown by the bolsheviks, longing for the past days, our fallen national statehood we read in his letter addressed his pen friend Azer Buzovnali:

*Getdi əldən o keçən sevimli günlər, Azər,
Yakıyor şimdi qəmin gönlümü azər, Azər...
...Türklüyün varlığı qeyrə nə böyük qorxuymuş,
Dost-düşmən onu məhv etməyi istər, Azər!* [13, p.38].

The poets who kept alive the medieval tradition of writing letters at the beginning of the 20th century expressed their problems, what they wanted to say, and their inner feelings to each other through letters and

ghazals. Thus, the response letter written by Azer Buzovnali, who glorifies the same feelings in ghazal given above by S. Mansur, is noteworthy:

*Getdi əldən, o keçən günləri salma yadə
Gələcəkdə yenə var sevməli günlər, Mənsur!
Qalxışan məhvimizə məhv olur axırda özü,
Etmə bu barədə qəm, olma mükəddər, Mənsur* [9, p.126].

In the beginning of the 20th century, the poets who spoke with heartache about the humiliation, oppression, slavery, scholastic meetings that encouraged ignorance in the society, mobilized all their forces for the freedom of the motherland and the education of the people, described these emotions and dreams about the future in their ghazals as they are. In one of his ghazals, S. Mansur writes:

*Tərki-tən qıl, olasan kişvəri-doldarə mühacir,
Şəmi-pərvanə hədisin oxu, ey aşiqi-sadiq* [13, p.19]

The great writer A. Muznib, who dedicated all his activities to one goal and one cause, prefer the national freedom of the country and the people above all else, fearlessly says his word against the tyranny that oppresses our people, crushes them in the claws of slavery, chains their freedom and free speech:

*Pəncəyi-qəhri-qəzəbdə can verir nazlı Vətən,
Qəhr edir cümlə Vətən övladına hər bir yetən...* [15, p.20]

Understanding the aesthetic-cognitive, didactic-moral, educational importance of literature and poetry, the poets include universal, humanistic and multicultural values in their ghazals, and the infinity of content and aesthetic shades of ghazal prompted all three artists to use their pens on all topics. In this sense, A. Muznib [16, p.6], who “dedicated his life and youth to the struggle for the education of the motherland, freedom and the free living of the people”, who is considered the poet of the republican era and who sacrificed his life for the sake of the motherland and the nation, expressed this selflessness in his ghazals:

*Millətimdən çəkməyəm əl, xarü zar olsam da mən,
Dönməyəm əzmiyəm hərgiz tarü mar olsam da mən* [15, p.23]

Feelings of national patriotism, salvation of the state and the nation from slavery, love for our values and love of Turkishness are typical for ghazals of Azer Buzovnali, who lived and created in the first half of the 20th century, and the most famous of his ghazals in this style is ghazal “Hemvətenlərim” (“My Compatriots”):

*Həmvətenlər, yatmayın, yatmaq zərərdir
yatmayın!*

*Çıxdı gün, aləm işıqlandı, səhərdir, yatmayın!
...Fəl edər təmini-istiqlalımız, nə boş məqal,
Boş məqalə qabil olmaz hərgiz əxşasi-fəal...* [5, p.177-178].

S. Mansur, who understands the sanctity and responsibility of serving the motherland and the nation, repeatedly declares in his ghazals that he is fighting and that he will not turn back from his path:

*Xatirimdən sanma məhv olsun havayi-aşıyan
Ol həvəslə bəsləyəm könlümdə ümmidi-bülənd* [13, p.22]

Just as ghazals, which have different content, have a national-spiritual, moral-didactic, educational purpose, they were also the simplest means of expressing social-political and ideological thoughts. Through these ghazals, the poets inculcated internationalism along with demanding their rights and possessing national values, through ghazals, they turned to the youth, intellectual and literate generation, and expected from them courage and bravery, fearlessness against tyranny, firmness of conviction, and national unity. In ghazal written by Samad Mansur, we read:

*İllərcə səni qul edənə məhv edəcəksən,
Hər bir bəşəri kəndinə bilməklə bərabər!
...Birlik, yenə birlik demiş ərbabi-təsəvvür,
Beynəlmiləliyyə, ucalıq, aləmi-əkbar* [13, p.34]

A. Muznib, one of the leaders of the struggle for national independence, propagated not to submit to slavery in every artistic example he penned, and called the sons of motherland to unite and fight for freedom:

*Qalib olmaq istərisən hazır ol, bizzat özün,
Başqanın imdadı ilə fəthdən ümid kəs!
Zalimə qarşı durub, təslimi-can et, həqq üçün,
Haqq sözü təkrar qıl, təndə qılınca bir nəfəs* [15, p.30]

At the beginning of the 20th century, academician Tofiq Hacıyev, who touched on the linguistic characteristics of artistic style, points out the tendency of “nationalization manifested in lexical and grammatical norms as the most important aspect”, and notes that what “happened in the social and cultural environment created the linguistic landscape of the period in the artistic language” [11, p.259-260]. Poets who wrote poems in various bahrs of aruz created national examples of ghazals using words of Turkic origin in radif and rhymes. In such ghazals, radifs and rhymes mostly consisted of verbs. From this point of view, Azer Buzovnali’s “Gelir”, “İstemez”, “Biler” [7], “Kash ki”, “Meni”, “Gelmedi” [8], A. Muznib’s “Bilməz”, “Bak”, “Dedi”, “Eylar” [15], in S. Mansur’s ghazals with radifs “Var”, “Görün”, “Gostar” simplicity and naturalness coming from our folklore and folk literature are noticeable [13]. In A. Muznib’s ghazal titled “Millət” those who are indifferent to our mother tongue, those who leave their own native language and show love for foreign languages are accused, and those who do not own the native language and national values are harshly criticized:

*Barı əlində saxla bu milli lisanını,
Hifz eylə milli adətini varikən macal.
Bax, büsbütün çoluq-cocuq əcnəbiləşib,
Dil yox, libas yox, hünər az, vaxt pürmahal...
Hər kim ki, öz dilin atub, özgə dil tutar,
Sanma o dillidir, yox, oduq ən birinci lal* [15, p.31]

Azer Buzovnali conveys his doleful and sad mood with artistic language, at the end of ghazal he complains about his fortune and sorrowful fate:

*Bu nə rəftardır, ey çərxi-zalim binəvalərlə,
Həmişə qarşıları onları dərdü bəlalərlə* [8, p.132]

In general, the spirit of complaint has found its artistic expression in most of the lyric poems written in various genres. A. Muznib also has many ghazals in

which his spiritual world is expressed in words, complaining about his time, people's indifference, and the destruction of his life:

Fəğan, dövrən bu dünyanın əlhəzər olduğun bilməz,

Təbii süslü əcnasən həp ezdad olduğun bilməz [15, p.70]

J. Abdullayev draws attention to the fact that artistic thinking is equal to the expressive power of words in works of art and writes that “one of the main conditions of literary perfection is the unity of meaning and emotion in works of art” [1, p.62]. We clearly see the unity of these conditions in ghazals of A. Buzovnali, A. Muznib and S. Mansur. Seeing the demands of the times and the progress of the nations, the literary world and pen masters wish their people to experience these advancements as well, they express that acquiring education, science, and knowledge opens all the difficult and closed doors. Azer Buzovnali has reflected many problems that concern the society, called people, especially the youth, to be educated, and propagated to be educated and knowledgeable:

*Hər millətin ki, elmə yox aləmdə rəğbəti,
Alsun gözü önünə cəhan içrə zilləti* [3].

Or in his another ghazal:

*Rəhi-məktəbdən azma çün bu yol rahi-həqiqətdir,
Bu yoldan azmayanlar vasil olmuş şani-valayə* [3].

saying that he has believed the role of education and training in the formation of a healthy environment in society is great, and the opening of schools will save the country from both ignorance and the chain of illiteracy.

S. Mansur, who made the main line of all his works the promotion of enlightenment, the glorification of human values, and the struggle for the freedom of the motherland, turning his face to his compatriots recommended them to stand up, embrace knowledge and science, and tear the veil of ignorance from their eyes:

*Qalx, pərdeyi-cəhli uzağa at göz özündən,
Məruz ola ənsarına ta qayeyi-əhmər* [13, p.34]

The early 20th century was a time of intense political upheaval, cultural change, and being disturbed of social balance. The intellectual, educated class and people of science of this era had to play the role of the beacon of society, and of course they did. In this sense, the poets, publicists and those who have other professions, who make up the intellectual class of the society and have a unique position in it, were considered pen masters that they reflected what they saw, reflected the wrong-right, false-true with an artistic language. A. Buzovnali, A. Muznib, and S. Mansur, who were pen masters and were not indifferent to what was happening in the society, conveyed their words by the language of poetry, embodied their thoughts about art, words and artists, and their opinions based on their great and comprehensive observations in their ghazals. According to them, poem should not only glorify lovers, but should be a mirror of society. Also, the form and content should complement each other, words should stand for meaning and logic, and the meaning should be deep. In the absence of these features, the poem cannot be considered a perfect example of poetry. Azer Buzovnali, a

master artist of the time, touches on this issue in one of his ghazals, the poet complains that the world is filled in untalented writers, and there are very few real poets:

*Güzgü tək olmalıdır nikü bədə şairlər,
Bilirəm borclu gər mən də bu işdə özümü* [8, p.136].

*...Gər mənim də var bir az hissəm fünuni-şeyrdə,
Qardaşım Vahid, vəli ustadi-əzəm başqadır.*

Mötəğid əşxaslar çox varsa məni-bikəsə,

Leyk səntək qədrdən şəxsi-mükərrəm başqadır [7, p.190].

S. Mansur, who wrote a imitative poem to genius Fuzuli's ghazal with radif “Soz”, talks about the greatness of the power of words, saying that the world exists through words, that the word, which is the means of expression of cognition, is chosen skillfully, and that the use of inappropriate words causes complications, the poet writes:

*Sözdür rizqi-nəfs üçün əshabi-sülh, alati-cəng,
Qəlbi-məcruhun şəfası tiği-cövhərdir söz...*

...Natiq öz nitqində izhar eyləyər idrakını,

Çünki hissü qəlb təşxisindədir meyar söz... [13, p. 20]

S. Mansur, who wished for the enlightenment of the people and was worried about their future, knew that the way to salvation was in learning and reading and writing. The poet who says that having a great responsibility of the pen masters in this way, believes that the pen with a figurative language will overcome ignorance, slavery, backwardness, injustice and lawlessness in his ghazal with radif “Galam”:

*Ehrazi-məqamat üçün alat qələmdir
Həm aləti-təhsili-kəmalat qələmdir...*

...Çün tərbiyeyi-növi-başəərdir ona möhtac,

Vazeh bu kim, ümmül-ədəbiyyat qələmdir [13, p. 19].

These ghazals, which mainly illuminate lyrical-amorous, patriotic, religious-mystical motives, are also an artistic picture of the socio-political and cultural landscape of the period, are the reflection of each writer's individual style, unique language and artistic-aesthetic thought. It seems clear from ghazals, which show different themes and artistic-aesthetic shades, that the literary-technical embodiment of the classical poetry style, the use of poetic figures of speech express the artistic-aesthetic feelings of all three writers. This especially comes from the requirements of the chosen form and the rules that the classical literary school sets for fiction. In these ghazals it is reflected the poetic imagination of each poet, their mental worlds reflecting how they see the environment, society and environment. They described in figurative language the cultural life, social and political atmosphere of the time they lived, sometimes with hidden meanings, and used classical poem technique in the most perfect way.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, let's say that since the literary and cultural landscape of the beginning of the 20th century being examined in the context of Soviet literary criticism until the 90s of the 20th century, some issues have been distorted, or discussed superficially, or subjected to the improvisation of the political conjuncture. In this

sense, we tried to take into account the social and political conditions of the time, the demands of the time, as well as the sensitivity of the political regime and society to the artistic word when analyzing the poets' ghazals involved in the study. It should be noted that during an objective analysis, it becomes clear that beginning of the 20th century Azerbaijani poetry, which is a landscape of a complicated historical period, is neither less important than the previous nor subsequent stages due to its ideological-artistic value and reflection of national-spiritual values. Because this poetry, which is a figurative relic of the nation's history and spiritual world, does not lag at all from the historical works and sources as a reflection of all the historical-social, cultural changes, life, and social opinion of different poles of society experienced by the people at the beginning of the last century. The study of this rich source - national literature, which was formed at the beginning of the 20th century, creates a basis for illuminating of a certain page of the history of Azerbaijan, for studying the literary life and artistic-aesthetic opinion of the society in a comprehensive and consistent way of following the poetry branch of Azerbaijani literature, which reflects the cultural and spiritual ideals and national values of the East and the West.

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